

Benzidine Rearrangement in the Heterocyclic Series. Part I.

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The present investigation was undertaken with the expectation of obtaining 4:5-disubstituted aminothiodiazines (I) which will result by the interaction of halogenated ketones with 1-substituted thiosemicarbazides.

When equimolecular quantities of 1-phenylthiosemicarbazide and a halogenated ketone, such as monochloroacetone, ω -bromoacetophenone or *p*-methyl- ω -bromoacetophenone, were shaken in absolute alcohol at the room temperature, the hydrochloride or hydrobromide of the condensation product was obtained in quantitative yield. The base has the same composition as (I), where $R = C_6H_5$, CH_3 , or *p*- $CH_3 \cdot C_6H_4$. These bases, on acetylation with acetic anhydride, yielded *monoacetyl* derivatives. Moreover, they were found to give colour reactions with concentrated sulphuric acid (*vide* Experimental part).

The above bases, which are formed by the elimination of a molecule of water and a molecule of hydrochloric or hydrobromic acid, may have one of the following structures :

Of these the last three contain either an imino or a hydrazino group. It was, therefore, considered desirable to study the action of aqueous hydrochloric acid on the condensation products. These would be hydrolysed to ammonia or phenyl hydrazine in case they possessed any of the last three structures (III, IV, V), thus:

Accordingly each of the bases was boiled with dilute hydrochloric acid for 5-15 minutes. The products were almost quantitatively converted into isomeric bases by the influence of this reagent. These (isomeric bases) dissolved in concentrated sulphuric acid without developing any colour and yielded, on acetylation with acetic anhydride, *diacetyl* derivatives, and were found to be diacid bases, the chloroplatinates having the composition, $\text{B}_2\text{H}_2\text{PtCl}_6$. These results are not consistent with any of the formulae (I), (III), (IV) or (V), some of which can explain the isomeric change in a satisfactory manner but fail to account for the general chemical properties.

On the assumption that the bases have the structure (II), the isomeric transformation brought about by hydrochloric acid may be regarded as an instance of benzidine rearrangement.

A very similar case has been placed on record by Fargher and Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 116, 222; *cf.* also Pyman and Ravald, *ibid.*, 1920, 117, 1426) who found that in the reduction of 2-benzene-azoglyoxaline (X) with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid, the main product was 2-amino-4-*p*-aminophenylglyoxaline (XII), the rearrangement obviously taking place through the intermediate hydrazo compound (XI).

According to these investigators (*loc. cit.*) "the occurrence of a rearrangement of the benzidine type in a five-membered heterocyclic nucleus seems remarkable at first sight, but a closer inspection of the formula shows that the conjugated system connecting the 2- and 5-carbon atoms of the glyoxaline ring is similar to that existing in the benzene nucleus."

In the present instance the five-membered heterocyclic ring happens to be a thiazole of which the 2- and 5-carbon atoms are connected by a conjugated system exactly similar to that present in the glyoxaline ring mentioned above. It is, moreover, a hydrazo compound and indeed a benzidine rearrangement is to be expected. The formula (IX) for the isomeric bases easily explains the formation of diacetyl derivatives. A direct and more conclusive evidence has been furnished by the formation of *p*-acetyl-aminobenzoic acid on oxidation of the diacetyl compound of formula IX ($R=CH_3$) by acid permanganate solution. This result also eliminates the possibility that the bases had undergone semidine rearrangement yielding compounds of the type (XIII) or (XIV).

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Phenylhydrazino-4-phenyl-1:3-thiazole: Formula II ($R=C_6H_5$).
 —Finally powdered 1-phenylthiosemicarbazide (1.7 g.) and ω -brom-acetophenone (2 g.) were shaken with absolute alcohol (15 c.c.) without the application of heat. The components gradually dissolved and the solution became warm. After a few minutes crystals separated out. Ether (20 c.c.) was added to the product and the greenish white crystals were collected, washed with ether and dried (3.4 g.). The *hydrobromide* was dissolved in a mixture of warm pyridine and alcohol, and diluted with water. The colourless needles of the base, which separated out, were twice recrystallised from dilute acetone; m.p. 191°. (Found: C, 67.30; H, 5.00. $C_{14}H_{11}N_2S$ requires C, 67.42; H, 4.87 per cent.).

It gave a bluish green colour with concentrated sulphuric acid; the colour vanished on dilution. It is soluble in cold acetone, hot benzene or pyridine, and only sparingly so in ether or alcohol.

The *acetyl* derivative was twice crystallised from alcohol in glistening transparent needles, m. p. 161°. (Found: N, 13.56. $C_{17}H_{13}ON_2S$ requires N, 13.59 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on the above Base: Formation of 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-p-aminophenyl-1:3-thiazole.

The base (1 g.) was boiled during 10 minutes with 100 c.c. of 2.5N—hydrochloric acid. The solution was cooled, filtered and the filtrate was made alkaline with ammonia. An oil separated out which hardened in the course of a few hours. This was removed, washed with cold water and dried (0.85 g.). It was crystallised from dilute alcohol using animal charcoal as a decoloriser. Pale yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 193-4°, were obtained. (Found: C, 67.84; H, 5.54; S, 11.73. $C_{14}H_{11}N_2S$ requires C, 67.42; H, 4.87; S, 11.98 per cent.).

It does not give any color reaction with concentrated sulphuric acid. This base is also obtained if the condensation between the thiosemicarbazide and the bromoketone is carried out in boiling alcoholic solution for about 10 minutes. It is easily soluble in alcohol, benzene, acetone, chloroform and pyridine, sparingly in ether and ligroin.

The *hydrochloride* crystallises from dilute hydrochloric acid in colorless needles. It decomposed above 260°. (Found: Cl, 20·18. $C_{11}H_{13}N_2S$, 2HCl, H_2O requires Cl, 19·88 per cent.).

The *picrate* formed yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 114·85° d.

The *chloroplatinate* formed yellow microscopic crystals which had no m.p. (Found: Pt, 28·6%. $C_{11}H_{13}N_2S$, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt, 28·80 per cent.).

2-Acetylamino-4-phenyl-5-p-acetylamino-phenyl-1:3-thiazole.

On adding acetic anhydride to the base the latter dissolved with evolution of considerable heat. On boiling the solution for a short time, a crystalline product separated out. The whole was allowed to cool, the solid was collected, washed with alcohol, and crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and dilute alcohol as long, white needles, m. p. 285°. These, however, changed into transparent, pale brown, compact prisms, m. p. 285-86°, on keeping for a few days in contact with its mother-liquor. (Found: N, 12·06. $C_{18}H_{17}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 11·97 per cent.).

2-Phenylhydrazino-4-p-tolyl-1:3-thiazole: Formula II(R=p-C₆H₄),

1-Phenylthiosemicarbazide (3·4 g.) and *p*-methyl-*o*-bromacetophenone (4·2 g.) were shaken with absolute alcohol (25 c. c.) in a flask. These went into solution with rise of temperature and colorless needles began to separate out almost immediately. The flask was cooled and ether (75 c. c.) was added. The *hydrobromide* of the condensation product was filtered off, washed with ether and dried. The yield was quantitative. The base, 2-phenylhydrazino-4-*p*-tolyl-1:3-thiazole was liberated using pyridine. When crystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol, it formed long, colorless needles, m. p. 186°. (Found: N, 15·02. $C_{16}H_{17}N_2S$ requires N, 14·95 per cent.).

It is easily soluble in acetone, pyridine, or ether but sparingly in alcohol. It gave a deep green coloration with concentrated sulphuric acid.

The *acetyl* derivative, obtained by heating the base with acetic anhydride, crystallised from alcohol in colourless, soft star-like aggregates, melting at 146°. (Found: N, 18·12. $C_{18}H_{17}ON_2S$ requires N, 18·00 per cent.).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on the above Base: Formation of 2-Amino-4-p-tolyl-5-p-aminophenyl-1:3-thiazole.

The base (1.5 g.) was boiled with 100 c. c. of 2.5N-hydrochloric acid for about 15 minutes. The yield of the isomeride amounted to 1.4 g. It is easily soluble in methyl or ethyl alcohol, pyridine, acetone or ether. It separated from dilute alcohol in pale brown needles melting at 182°. (Found: N, 14.82. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2S$ requires N, 14.95 per cent.). It gave only a very faint yellowish green color with concentrated sulphuric acid.

The diacetyl derivative, namely *2-acetylamino-4-p-tolyl-5-p-acetylamino-phenyl-1:3-thiazole* crystallised from glacial acetic acid in white, slender needles, m. p. 290°. (Found: N, 11.44. $C_{20}H_{18}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 11.51 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid in long, colorless needles. (Found: Cl, 19.92. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2S, 2HCl$ requires Cl, 20.06 per cent.).

The *chloroplatinate* was obtained in yellow microscopic crystals, which had no m. p. (Found: Pt, 27.84. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2S, H_2PtCl_6, H_2O$ requires Pt, 27.51 per cent.).

The *picrate* crystallised in yellow microscopic crystals, m. p. 215° (with previous sintering and decomposition).

2-Phenylhydrazino-4-methyl-1:3-thiazole: Formula II (R=CH₃).

1-Phenylthiosemicarbazide (3.2 g.) and monochloroacetone (2 g.) were shaken with 25 c. c. of absolute alcohol, till the former had completely dissolved. The solution was allowed to stand for a few minutes, and treated with pyridine (7 c.c.) and water (50 c.c.). The needle-shaped crystals, which separated out, were collected, washed with water, and recrystallised from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 179°. (Found: C, 58.83; H, 5.62. $C_{16}H_{11}N_2S$ requires C, 58.53; H, 5.36 per cent.).

2-Phenylhydrazino-4-methyl-1:3-thiazole is easily soluble in benzene or acetone but almost insoluble in ligroin. It imparted a rose-red coloration to concentrated sulphuric acid. The substance turned brownish red on keeping for days or on heating above 150°.

The *acetyl* derivative formed colorless shining needles or plates, m. p. 232°. (Found: N, 17.08. $C_{18}H_{15}ON_2S$ requires N, 17.00 per cent.).

It is easily soluble in benzene, ether, chloroform or dilute hydrochloric acid, but sparingly in benzine.

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on the above Base: Formation of 2-Amino-4-methyl-5-p-aminophenyl-1:3-thiazole.

The base (1.2 g.) was boiled with normal hydrochloric acid (25 c.c.) for about 5 minutes. Shining plates were obtained on making the cold solution alkaline with caustic soda. The dried material (1 g.) was twice recrystallised from dilute methyl alcohol using animal charcoal. It forms pale-brown shining plates, m. p. 181°. (Found: N, 20.84. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2S$ requires N, 20.48 per cent.).

It is easily soluble in alcohol or pyridine but sparingly in benzene or chloroform. It did not respond to the color reaction characteristic of its isomeride.

The *hydrochloride* crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid solution in long, silky needles which decomposed above 240°. It contains 2 molecules of water of crystallisation. (Found: Cl, 22.59. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2S, 2HCl, 2H_2O$ requires Cl, 22.62 per cent.). On drying in a steam-oven only $1\frac{1}{2}$ molecules of water could be driven off. (Found: Cl, 24.56. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2S, 2HCl, \frac{3}{2}H_2O$ requires Cl, 24.74 per cent.).

The *chloroplatinate* was obtained as small, orange pointed needles. (Found: Pt, 30.82. $C_{10}H_{11}N_2S, H_2PtCl_6, H_2O$ requires Pt, 30.80 per cent.).

The *picrate* formed yellow, star-like aggregates, m. p. 214° (with decomp.)

Benzylidene Derivative.—To a hydrochloric acid solution of the base, benzaldehyde was added drop by drop and shaken when a deep yellow crystalline precipitate immediately separated out. This was collected, washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and dried. The product (hydrochloride of the monobenzylidene derivative) was then dissolved in pyridine and the base precipitated by water. From dilute methyl alcohol it separated in yellow needles, m. p. 177°. (Found: N, 14.32. $C_{17}H_{14}N_2S$ requires N, 14.38 per cent.).

The *diacetyl* derivative, *2-acetylamino-4-methyl-5-p-acetylamino-phenyl-1:3-thiazole* was obtained from dilute pyridine in long colorless needles, which gradually changed into hard prismatic crystals, m. p. 292°, on being kept in contact with the mother-liquor for several days. (Found: N, 14.65. $C_{14}H_{15}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 14.53 per cent.).

Oxidation of 2-Acetylamino-4-methyl-5-p-acetylamino-phenyl-1:3-thiazole.

The acetyl derivative (2 g.) was dissolved in acetone (150 c.c.) and to it dilute sulphuric acid (125 c. c. of 20 per cent.) was added when the substances was precipitated in a fine state of division. A 2% solution of potassium permanganate was gradually dropped in with constant shaking at the ordinary temperature when the acetyl derivative gradually went into solution. The addition of permanganate was stopped when the pink color persisted for a few seconds, about 135 c. c. being required. The solution was then just made alkaline with a concentrated solution of sodium carbonate and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated on the water-bath till crystals of sodium sulphate began to separate. It was then filtered off and the filtrate acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid when a white precipitate of *p*-acetylamino benzoic acid was obtained. This was collected, washed with a little cold water and dried (0.8 g.). On crystallisation from water (using animal charcoal), it formed long glistening plates, m. p. 255-56°. The m.p. of this substance when mixed with a pure specimen of *p*-acetylamino benzoic acid remained unchanged. The identity was further established by a nitrogen estimation. (Found: N, 8.01. $C_9H_9O_2N$ requires N, 7.82 per cent.).